

THE IMPORTANCE OF TRANSFORMING THE PREPARATION OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY IN A DIGITALIZED ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *The article emphasizes the importance of transforming the readiness of future primary school teachers for professional activity in a digital environment, which will help prepare future specialists to work in various fields. Achieving professional maturity in the process of problem situations and data processing is aimed at developing students' professional competence and increasing the professional activity of future teachers.*

Keywords: *digital technologies, digital transformation, educational resources, teacher, quality of education, self-education, professional activity, professional training.*

The development of the readiness of future primary school teachers to use digital educational resources in the selected areas should be based on ideas about the content and features of future professional activity. This helps to prepare future specialists for work in various fields. The possibilities of the competency-based approach are created taking into account the relevance of developing students' professional competence, achieving professional maturity in problem situations and data processing.

When integrating this practice into curricula, it is important to choose pedagogical approaches that are adaptable to the digital environment. First of all, the main approaches to training aimed at developing the readiness of future primary school teachers to use digital educational resources in their professional activities should be pedagogical approaches that allow for the most complete integration of student learning into their professional activities, taking into account educational activities and solving specific problems. That is why, we have chosen the following approaches as the basis for approaches to developing students' professional training in the digital environment[1]:

- a professional-competency-based approach aimed at developing students' knowledge and skills in conditions of maximum convergence of educational and professional activities in solving specific professional problems;

- a competence-based approach, in which the priority is not the parameters specified in the structure of professional activity, but the expected results in the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities by students, effective methods of activity; It is not the number of hours, the learning process and the amount of information received that develops, but a person's ability to act in various problem situations.

In our study, we understand the competence-based approach to professional pedagogical education as a unified system of organizational and technological support for the process of training teachers in setting goals, selecting content, identifying the main, general and special types

of pedagogical activity that guarantee a high level and explain the effectiveness of the professional and pedagogical activity of the teacher [2].

Digital technologies in education are undoubtedly a way of organizing an educational environment based on digital technologies. Therefore, digital transformation of the education sector is the process of updating the planned educational results, educational content, methods and organizational forms of educational work, as well as assessing the achieved results in the context of a rapidly developing digital environment in order to radically improve the education system, that is, based on the results of each user, the "principles of the digital environment" are achieved, that is, based on educational services and digital services, etc., the established parameters are achieved that reflect the level of development of the information and telecommunications infrastructure of educational organizations, the digital competencies of participants in the educational process, the level of access to information technologies [3].

Digital transformation is not only an education reform. This is also a multi-year program of activities that affects all levels of education. As in the case of the provision of services and material production, work on the digital transformation of education should not only be focused on the result at all stages of the program implementation, but also contribute to improving the quality of work of higher education organizations. Digital technologies help to radically improve the quality of education for students, develop all the necessary skills in them, subsequently form the ability to actively (consciously and creatively) use all available digital tools, materials and services. The basis of the digital transformation of higher education institutions is the transition to a personalized organization of the educational process, in which the introduction and use of digital technologies is most effective. Changing the working methods of educational organizations requires changing the regulatory framework for the digital transformation of education. Without implementing this in practice, it is difficult to implement this structure without comprehensive testing and refinement on the ground on innovative digital educational platforms during a broad legal experiment [5].

Indeed, digital transformation of education is a "set of changes affecting all interconnected components of the education system (goal setting, content, learning process, quality assessment, management) and based on the adaptation of information and pedagogical technologies"[4].

"Digital didactics is the basis for the emergence of an integrative field of scientific knowledge, characterized by mutual adaptation and transfer of ideas from didactics, computer science and other pedagogical disciplines studying digital technologies"[6].

"The digital educational environment is an increasingly complex system of conditions and opportunities that presupposes the presence of an infrastructure based on information and communication technologies and provides a set of digital technologies and resources for training, development, socialization and education of the individual"[7].

"The digital learning process is an organized and structured learning process that takes into account the individual and collective learning activities of students, based on the use of digital technologies with the participation of a teacher in digital learning, aimed at developing digital competencies"[5].

Digital competencies include a set of knowledge, skills and competencies required to successfully solve professional problems.

"Digitalization of the educational process in particular is a complete adaptation of the elements of the educational process, digital technologies and tools used in the educational process

to solving pedagogical problems in order to maximize the use of the potential didactic capabilities of digital technologies" [3].

It should be emphasized that digital teaching aids are a set of methods, approaches, technologies and tools used in digital didactics [6].

The concept of digital transformation of education is studied by a number of authors from different positions. Thus, "digitalization arose in connection with the development of information and communication technologies." E.L. Vartanova, M.I. Makseenko, S.S. Smirnov gave their scientific conclusions on the problem of digital transformation of education. "That is, the digital transformation of education should be undoubtedly considered as an infrastructural, managerial, behavioral and cultural component of the content of education," they explained [6].

The following topics were studied: "The influence and features of digital transformation on the teaching of individual subjects, the problem of preparing teachers for the digital educational process" [Brown, 2001], "functional changes in the activities of teachers in the digital educational environment, the role of a modern teacher in the context of the digital transformation of modern education and its implementation" [Nevolina, 2022], "prospects for the introduction of digital technologies in the educational process" [Kamolovich, 2022]. "When discussing the role and importance of digital technologies in education, among their advantages, it is especially noted that e-learning can create potential conditions for the population with limited access to higher education [6].

Digitalization of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is determined by the following main objectives:

- providing educational institutions with broadband Internet access, as well as equipping educational institutions with modern digital technologies that will increase the availability and diversity of educational materials;
- creating a unified knowledge base at the republican level;
- increasing the level of use of digital technologies in educational organizations of various levels, including electronic and distance learning;
- monitoring the quality of education and assessing the use of e-learning in educational organizations;
- "creating an ecosystem of continuous learning, including identifying and supporting talent in all areas";

- It is significant that it is aimed at "training highly qualified personnel who meet new requirements and key competencies for the education system" [1].

Figure 1. Potential of digital educational resources

Wide access to educational content: Digital resources allow teachers to access a wide range of educational content. This, in turn, helps them enrich the content of their lessons. For example, resources such as e-books, teaching materials, video tutorials, and online courses expand the knowledge base of teachers.

Possibility of personalization of the learning process: The learning process can be individualized with the help of digital resources, taking into account the specific needs of each student. This gives teachers the opportunity to use a variety of interactive and personalized resources to develop the individual abilities of students.

Create an interactive and interconnected learning environment: Using digital platforms, teachers can offer students interactive tasks, tests, and project work. During this process, students consolidate their knowledge, gain a deeper understanding of the topics, and develop skills in applying knowledge in practice.

Development of digital skills: Primary school teachers develop their technological skills by working with digital resources. At the same time, they learn to create educational materials, use online learning platforms, work with electronic communication tools and use various programs to assess students' knowledge.

Implementation of innovative approaches: with the help of digital resources, teachers will be able to implement modern innovative approaches in their educational processes, including distance learning, blended learning and gamification methods. This makes the learning process more interesting and interactive[1].

Solving the problem of developing a future primary school teacher's "readiness to use digital educational resources in professional activities" requires an analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature devoted to the definitions of professional readiness and "teacher readiness for pedagogical activity".

In the experience of foreign scientists in defining the essence and characteristics of electronic-digital education, in particular, Borje Holmberg [Brown, 2001], Loboda O.V., Grudin A.M., Alimagadov S.A., Zenkova T.L., Orlova O.I., Sheveleva A.A. Research by experts such as "emphasize that while the digital education system is flexible in one respect, it is an extremely complex process in another." Consequently, an extremely complex digital education system will inevitably lead to counterproductive results, since it becomes increasingly difficult to control a complex system [7].

In his research, when creating a methodological system for teaching computer science in higher education institutions, U.Sh. Begimkulov relies on the methods of informatization of the educational process. He gave a pedagogical justification for the introduction of information and communication technologies into the system of higher pedagogical education, developed substantive and regulatory aspects of training teaching staff in the field of information technology in education [3].

In the research work of M.Zh. Saidova, "the importance of improving the professional competence and training of future primary school teachers in the context of distance learning, the methodology for improving professional competence and training, a comparative analysis of professional and professional-methodological competence, the possibilities of improving the components of the mechanism for the formation of professional-methodological competence of future primary school teachers, their integration with professional activities" are substantiated [8].

One of our local scientists, S.E. Nizomkhonov, in his study states that "a new stage in the development of society leads to the process of "digitalization", which ensures the priority of modernization of education with a modern information environment, the creation of effective opportunities for digitalization in the process of informatization" [8].

An analysis of scientific literature has shown that there are studies devoted to the issues of professional training of future teachers in the context of digitalization of education (L.V. Bocharova, Yu.S. Branovsky, S.D. Karakozov, V.V. Laptev, M.P. Lapchik, A.V. Mogilev, E.A. Rakitina, I.V. Robert, O.G. Smolyaninova, A.A. Temerbekova, L.A. Kharitonova, etc.).

According to N. Baituraeva, "scientific research is being conducted to improve the pedagogical skills and intellectual creative competence of future specialists based on the development of creative competence, which is considered the main stage in the process of training future primary school teachers in the global education system" [7].

I.L. Bim wrote that this implies and implies the acquisition of practical knowledge through information and communication technologies, which serves as the basis for self-regulation and self-correction. Over the past 10-15 years, profound changes have occurred in the practice of teaching information and communication technologies in Uzbekistan. International assessment programs (TIMSS, PISA, PIRLS) have also set a new level of assessment of the professional development of future primary school teachers. In this regard, it can be said that the use of information and communication technologies is becoming increasingly important in the process of forming professional communicative competencies of primary school students through the study of a foreign language, since they acquire sufficient knowledge and skills in their professional activities [8].

M.I. Dyachenko, L.A. Kandybovich distinguish the following components in the structure of readiness for professional activity: motivational, including the presence of interest in the profession, a positive attitude towards professional activity; provision of knowledge about the

features of a particular professional activity, its specificity; efficient, including possessing the necessary knowledge, skills, professional abilities, work methods, etc.; arbitrariness, which consists in the ability to self-manage in the performance of their functional tasks; evaluator, including the ability to evaluate their own professional activity, correlate it with the activities of masters in a particular field, etc. [1]

A.G. Moroz's approach to identifying the components of preparation for pedagogical activity is close to V.A. Slastenin's position: "theoretical preparation for educational activity (knowledge, skills and abilities in subjects, teaching methods, desire for development, self-improvement); practical preparation (ability to apply acquired knowledge in practice, plan and organize work, clearly choose from various methods, techniques and technologies of teaching those that will lead to high results of educational work)." To the above-listed components of readiness for pedagogical activity, the scientist adds three more: "ideological and political preparation, including stable morality, broad outlook, the presence of a high culture of the teacher; the necessary level of development of pedagogical abilities, that is, the presence of pedagogical attention, imagination, observation, pedagogical thinking, tact in communication, managerial, organizational abilities, etc.; professional and pedagogical orientation of the teacher's personality" [3].

Since we consider professional training to be the initial level of professional competence, we do not stop at the stage of retraining of teaching staff. We distinguish the following stages of developing the readiness of a future primary school teacher to use digital educational resources:

the first stage is developing motivation to use digital educational resources in primary school and implementing existing (initial) competencies in the process of professional pedagogical training;

the second stage is gaining experience in solving professional problems of a primary school teacher using a digital resource center based on general professional content;

the third stage is improving the experience of solving professional problems of primary school teachers in the process of studying methodological disciplines with the help of a central training center. The content of each stage of developing the readiness of a future primary school teacher to use digital resources is disclosed in the description of the formative experiment.

The above represents the conceptual provisions of the methodology for developing the readiness of a future primary school teacher to use digital educational resources[8].

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